

Unlocking the Potential of Open Research Software in Acoustics

Nantes, 29-30 August 2024

The Future of Acoustics with Open Research Software

Maarten Hornikx

Department of the Built Environment

TU/e

Welcome, collaboration mode, and program

- Interactive workshop: presentations, feedback, questions, discussions
- For potential research output from workshop (report, paper) <https://tinyurl.com/Open-Acoustics-IC>
- For all attendees (on-site and online): write all your comments, questions and remarks in our collaborative HackMD log: <https://tinyurl.com/Open-Acoustics>
- We will try to address the questions during the workshop, and also welcome everyone to interact at HackMD
- We don't have all answers or knowledge, we target a workshop that brings our community further, that inspires you to be active on open research software.

Program

Day 1 - Thursday Afternoon:

2:00 PM - 2:15 PM: Registration

2:15 PM - 3:00 PM: The Future of Acoustics with Open Research Software. *Maarten Hornikx (TU/e)*

3:00 PM - 3:45 PM: Presentation of best practices examples on sharing research software from own work, which is based on open research software on GitHub/Zenodo. *Huiqing Wang (TU/e)*

3:45 PM – 4:00 PM: Coffee break

4:00 PM – 5:00 PM: Speaker Sessions

Pyroomacoustics: A software package aimed at the rapid development and testing of audio array processing algorithms. *Eric Bezzam (EPFL)*

Noise Modelling: A tool designed to produce environmental noise maps on very large urban areas. *Pierre Aumond (UMRAE- Université Gustave Eiffel)*

Program

Day 2 – Friday morning:

9:00 AM - 9:45 AM: Instructions and guidelines for acceleration of sharing research software, following best practices. *Maarten Hornikx, (TU/e)*

9:45 AM - 10:45 AM:

Virtual Acoustics: A software for simulating and auralizing acoustic environments.

Lukas Aspöck (RWTH)

Soundscapy: A python library for analysing and visualising soundscape assessments.

Andrew Mitchell (UCL)

10:45 AM – 11:00 AM: Coffee break

11:00 AM - 12:00 PM: Panel Discussion: Open Challenges and Future Directions

12:00 PM – 13:00 PM: Closing Remarks and Lunch

Our open research software practices, and opinions

A Mentimeter welcome slide with a background of a network graph consisting of red dots connected by thin lines. The slide contains a QR code on the left, a join link at the top, the TU/e logo in the top right, and a central welcome message with a consent statement.

Join at menti.com | use code 7795 6674

TU/e

Welcome!

By participating in this Mentimeter, you agree that the Building Acoustics group at TU/e can use your answers for research purposes.

Vision and motivation

Sharing research software has a huge potential

- **Acceleration of science**
 - **Reproducibility and quality**
 - **Impact**
 - **Community and Sustainability**
 - ...
- It is still not good practice to share and collaborate on research software
- This workshop is about triggering a culture change and discussing best practices

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Examples

Improves impact and community

Phase 1: Warm Up: Completed Phase 2: Completed #neurips #supervised_learning #reinforcement_learning

NeurIPS 2023 CityLearn Challenge 2023

Using AI For Building's Energy Management

5,000 USD Cash Prizes
Co-authorship in Competition Solutions Paper

By Alcrowd & Intelligent Environments Lab & Energy Efficient Cities Initiative

53.7k 715 105 2602 12 Share

Overview Leaderboard Notebooks Discussion Insights Submissions Select Submissions Rules **Participate**

PROBLEM STATEMENTS

Forecast Track: CityLearn Challenge

Design Regression Models To Predict Load Profiles

10.2k 785

Control Track: CityLearn Challenge

Develop Energy Management Agent(s)

12.1k 1817

PARTICIPANTS

Participate

GETTING STARTED

JSON alcrowd file central agent 11 months ago

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CityLearn

This output is listed in the Digital Public Goods Alliance Registry and contributes to the following UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):

7 Affordable and Clean Energy 11 Sustainable Cities and Communities 13 Climate Action

CityLearn is an open source Farama Foundation Gymnasium environment for the implementation of Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (RL) for building energy coordination and demand response in cities [24, 26]. A major challenge for RL in demand response is the ability to compare algorithm performance [28]. Thus, CityLearn facilitates and standardizes the evaluation of RL agents such that different algorithms can be easily compared with each other.

Districts and cities have periods of high demand for electricity, which raise electricity prices and the need for the distribution of energy resources.

 Mendeley Data

Pilot Studio Benchmark for a Round Robin Test on Room Acoustics Wave-Based Simulations

Published: 8 September 2023 | Version 1 | DOI: 10.17632/62nm9fvh42.1
Contributor: Giulia Fratoni

Description

Broadband wave-based simulation methods have been applied to an increasing number of 3D virtual rooms thanks to recent scientific and computational advances. The present Round Robin Test (RRT) focuses on practical aspects of room acoustics simulation, using any wave-based approach (FEM, BEM, FDTD, FVTD, etc...). The overall goal is to share a solid benchmark platform, which can be helpful to acousticians, engineers, and scholars. The shared materials will allow running simulations with different wave-based techniques and by various operators starting from the same models and boundary conditions.

Expected outcomes:

- 1) Results are compared against measurements and among the simulation tools (ISO 3382 room criteria and frequency responses)
- 2) Uncertainty information for boundary conditions

The following materials are provided: 3D Model (SketchUp 2017), Measurements (ISO 3382), Sound absorption coefficients
Materials to be shared for implementing the Round Robin Test dataset: Simulated IRs (.wav), Boundary conditions employed (complex-valued surface impedances)

For more information about the case study: <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11062445>
You can send your interest and materials to giulia.fratoni2@unibo.it

[Download All 1.46 MB](#) ⓘ

Files

- 3D model
- Boundary conditions
- Measurements

A dark blue slide with a subtle wave pattern. In the top left corner is the Undabit logo, which consists of a white circle with a dot inside, followed by the text 'undabit' in white. The main text is centered and reads 'Future-proof Acoustic Simulations: Embrace Open Source Software with Undabit'. Below this is a paragraph: 'Cost-effective, high-Fidelity acoustic simulation for your design challenges: at Undabit we help you transition seamlessly to open source acoustic simulation software.' At the bottom center is a yellow button with the text 'Get in contact: first simulation free of charge' in white.

© undabit

Future-proof Acoustic Simulations: Embrace Open Source Software with Undabit

Cost-effective, high-Fidelity acoustic simulation for your design challenges: at Undabit we help you transition seamlessly to open source acoustic simulation software.

Get in contact: first simulation free of charge

Vision and motivation

My vision: for the sake of quality, reproducibility, collaboration and impact of research work,

Sharing research software in acoustics should be integral part of scientific practice, and the software should be regarded as part of scientific output

The value of research software will exceed the value of scientific papers alone

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Vision and motivation

Around 50 existing open research software in room acoustics*

- low level of collaboration
- None of the packages has a doi number...

*Homikx, M., Paganini, L., Serebrenik, A., Nolte, A., Wang, H., & Fichera, I. (2024). Building-acoustics-TU-Eindhoven/OSS_RoomAcoustics: v1.0.0 (v1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12655865>

Open software

- Free software movement formally founded in 1983
- Open-source software has been in use since 1998

Open-source software relates to source code that is made freely available for possible modification and redistribution, promoting collaboration

- With the advent of platforms such as GitHub (2008), GitLab and repositories such as Zenodo, sharing open-source software has become possible in a sustainable way, providing opportunities for collaboration in which the distributed version control system Git (2005)

My training as a researcher (2002-2011): traditional research approach

- Quality scientific training
- Targetting to publish results in scientific papers and at conferences
- No system/platform to share data, software

My work at TU/e (2012-2019): efforts in open research software

- Open software grant 2012 (EU Career Integration Grant)
- Python implementation (with blender as interface) openPSTD software was shared on GitHub and a website, which was connected to a journal paper [1].
- Software was downloaded regularly (>1800 times)

[1] Hornikx, M., Krijnen, T. and van Harten, L., 2016. openPSTD: The open source pseudospectral time-domain method for acoustic propagation. Computer Physics Communications, 203, pp.298-308.

My work at TU/e (2012-2019): efforts in open research software

- Efforts were made to build a new interface from scratch with a C++ code
- Contributions from our lab could not be made due to a too low level programming language (C++)
- The open source community around it did not come off the ground: lack of awareness and skills to attract and retain an active community around it

My work at TU/e (2012-2019): efforts in open research software

- Student assistants from computer science to work on the acceleration and the C++ version: they had too little experience to successfully finalize the project
- Researchers in the lab lacked skills as well as the culture to spend time on sustainable research software, meaning that this project came too early

My work at TU/e (2019): efforts in open research software

- Attempt for accelerating software at EU level ...
- Something needs to change in our field (flagship codes, community)

<https://cheese-coe.eu>

Research software is locked, these are the barriers

- Lack of incentives Traditionally, scientific publications are valued, research software is not
- Culture e.g. Not sharing research software gives author(s) the opportunity to write the next scientific publication(s) about it, or to further develop it. Solitary work hampers development and impact.
- Lack of training Good practice skills on how to programme for sharing, what platform to use for it and what licence to connect to it is generally missing. Researchers may simply not be willing to share software as they consider it as non-readable for others, or because they fear criticism to their software practices

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My work at TU/e (2019 – now): Three level approach on research software

- Development: Research and research software
- Culture: Creating an (international) community on open research software in acoustics
- Training: Exploration at individual and research group level

Development: Research (software) in room/environmental acoustics

- Discontinuous Galerkin method
- Diffusion equation method
- Hybrid method
- Equivalent scattering approach

Dingding Xie

Wouter Wittebol

Huiqing Wang

Development: acceleration Discontinuous Galerkin method

- Acceleration on high level programming language
- eScience center project
- Matlab: single precision + GPU, Python implementation (on [GitHub](#))

Culture/Community: Creating an (international) community on open research software

Culture/Community: Creating an (international) community on open research software

A new era of room acoustics simulation software:
from academic advances to a sustainable open-source project
and community

Culture/Community: Creating an (international) community on open research software

Further development
and validation
of room acoustics
modelling methods

Development
of a software prototype
of these methods

Creation of an
open-source community
for continuation beyond
the project timeframe

Culture/Community: User interface under development

★ LOGO | Application > Projects > Project title x > Initial design | + New | User icon

Demo simulation

Env settings | Materials | Source/Receiver

Default settings | Advanced settings

Range of frequency

65 | 125 | 250 | 500 | 1k | 2k | 390 Hz

Time of simulation

3 s

Sound pressure: 35 dB | Sound velocity: 250 | Mesh length: 5 cm

Method of calculation

Wave solver method (Iliaria) | Geometrical acoustics solver (Huyging) | Both methods together (longer time of simulation)

Other options

Filled with default values | Version control activated | Stop simulation time > 10 mins

Estimated time is : 3 minutes | Today is: 2024-Feb-11, 13:40 | Run the simulation

Grid size: 1x1 m | Volume: 116.43 m³

➤ Connection to DG and DE method
➤ Workshop to come!

Training at individual and research group level

Training in evaluating research software underlying scientific papers

Sharing our software on GitHub

Away days with team in 2021, 2023, 2024

- Training of open software skills via CodeRefinery
- Improving open research software
- Collaboration on research software

Under development: group strategy on open research software

Training at individual and research group level

Hands-on collaboration works!

Unlocking the barriers, we are doing that all together.

Lack of incentives

-> Incentives incoming! Software can be licenced and cited, it gets valued in institutional research assessments, open science awards arise, recognition in university systems and grant writing

Culture

-> There are examples of open software communities, development of platforms that make research software accessible

Lack of training

-> Training modules are available

Future of open research software in acoustics is bright, but...

We need joint activities to propel it further:

- Active, hands-on workshops where participants use, review and give feedback on each others software
- Workshops on benchmark cases
- Hackathons on challenges using open source software

We need a system to review software (behind papers)

We need a sustainable community around research software. Part of our own [open science community](#) in acoustics?

We need many of you to bring this forward 😊

Building and Room Acoustics

ASSA 2024
NOV. 4 – 8
EINDHOVEN

www.assaeindhoven.org

Computational Acoustics

The Future of Acoustics with Open Research Software

Maarten Hornikx, m.c.j.hornikx@tue.nl

